

1 Interrogating a novel *in-silico* model to determine helium plasma jet and 2 chemotherapy efficacy against B16F10 melanoma cells

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16 17 **Abstract**

18 We developed an *in-silico* approach to model B16F10 melanoma cell response to helium atmospheric
19 pressure plasma jet (APPJ) or/and doxorubicin drug (DOX). The *in-silico* model is informed by relevant
20 data from previously-published *in-vitro* experiments (cancer cell viability) providing detailed information
21 on (i) cell population number (N_{cell}) development during incubation, and (ii) probability values for apoptosis
22 ($\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$) and mitosis ($\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$) following cell subjection to plasma-conditioned RPMI-1640 medium
23 (PC-RPMI), DOX, and DOX combined with APPJ. When treating cancer cells with PC-RPMI and DOX
24 separately, at the smallest plasma duration ($d_{\text{plasma}}=15$ s) and DOX concentration ($c_{\text{DOX}}=0.05$ μM), only a
25 small decline in N_{c} , increase in $\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$ or/and decrease in $\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$ are measured with respect to the
26 control conditions (non-treated cancer cells). However, cell cytotoxicity is increasingly enhanced with
27 increasing d_{plasma} and c_{DOX} up to 120 s and 0.5 μM , respectively. At those highest values studied in *in-silico*,
28 simulated $\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$ are significantly larger than $\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$ resulting in a severe decrease in N_{cell} compared
29 to control, in agreement with the corresponding *in-vitro* experiments. Furthermore, cell treatments
30 combining the smallest two c_{DOX} (0.05 and 0.1 μM) with $d_{\text{plasma}}=15$ s, result in smaller N_{cell} , larger $\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$
31 and lower $\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$ compared to PC-RPMI and DOX effects alone. The present *in-silico* model is
32 particularly useful in plasma (cancer) medicine field since it can effectively simulate and quantify responses
33 of various cancers to APPJ or/and cancer drugs being strongly complementary to *in-vitro* experiments.

35 Atmospheric Pressure Plasma Jets (APPJ) are non-equilibrium discharges with very promising
36 applications in biomedicine. APPJ generate localized and controlled fluxes of reactive oxygen and nitrogen
37 species (RONS), (V)UV radiation and transient electric fields that can affect the functionality of biological
38 matter.^{1,2} At the same time, their gas temperature remains close to room temperature,^{3,4} thus avoiding
39 thermal damage of living tissues. Specifically, their efficacy and selectivity against cancer has been
40 demonstrated in *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* (or *in ovo*) studies through: (i) plasma radiation applied on cancer cells
41 maintained in liquid media or solid tumors in mice models (direct treatment), and (ii) buffered solutions (or
42 cell-growth media) irradiated by APPJ, with the conditioned liquid (containing newly formed RONS) being
43 put in interaction with cancer cells or injected in solid tumors (indirect treatment).⁵⁻⁷ Although APPJ
44 treatments have been shown effective against different cancers, e.g., normal transformed lung fibroblasts
45 (MRC5Vi),⁸ and squamous pharynx cell carcinomas (Fadu),⁹ they were not as effective in others [human
46 colon cancer cells (HCT116),⁸ and squamous tongue cell carcinomas (CAL27),⁹ respectively]. Thus,
47 increasing the duration of the plasma treatment or using APPJ as adjuvant therapy with other cancer
48 treatment strategies (chemotherapy, pulsed electric fields, etc.) may offer improved therapeutic
49 outcomes.^{5,10-12} It should be noted that APPJ treatments differ significantly from traditional invasive
50 therapies such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy. This is because APPJ generates key RONS inducing
51 cytotoxic effects in cancer cells, without affecting the healthy cells.⁶

52 To date, most research works about APPJ effect on neoplasia consider *in-vitro* and *in-vivo*
53 investigations, with much fewer reporting *in-silico* (computer models) studies. *In-silico* works in plasma
54 medicine have focused on the description of physical, chemical and biological processes that determine
55 plasma effects on cells, healthy or wounded skin, liquid-covered tissues, solid tumors, etc.¹³ Zero-
56 dimensional models have been used to investigate chemical kinetics occurring, for instance, in the plasma-
57 gas and/or plasma-liquid (inter)phases.^{14,15} Computational fluid dynamics models have been employed to
58 describe plasma interactions with conductive and non-conductive surfaces, and provide insights on
59 discharge dynamics, key RONS production (such as OH, NO, NO₂, H₂O₂, ¹O₂, etc.), electron and electric
60 field properties, and their transport efficiency to biological matter.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Molecular dynamics simulations
61 have been introduced to study interactions of plasma-generated RONS with biomolecules (in or around
62 cancer cells) and DNA, RONS penetration through cell membranes, plasma oxidation of proteins and so
63 on.^{19,20} Despite the progress made thus far in *in-silico*, no models of cancer cell dynamics induced by APPJ
64 have yet been proposed, the only exception being the work from Murphy *et al.*,²¹ using a 3D hybrid discrete-
65 continuum model to investigate tumor growth and apoptosis upon exposure to plasma-produced RONS.
66 Such models can be very complementary to *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* experiments for quantifying and better
67 understanding effects of APPJ (or other treatments) on various cancers in a non-invasive manner (e.g., less
68 animal studies).

In-vitro experiments

69
70 **FIG. 1.** (a) Graphical representation of the *in-vitro* experimental setup of B16F10 cells treated with DOX
71 or/and APPJ by Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*¹⁰; cancer cells were maintained in 0.5 mL of RPMI-1640 medium.
72 (b) In reference,¹⁰ quadruplicate cell treatments were performed using the four corner-wells of different 24-
73 well plates (S1–S4). After each treatment, cells were incubated for 48 h (t_{48h}), and their viability was
74 measured at t_{48h} (MTT colorimetric assay). (c) Experimental (red), counted after t_0 , t_4h , t_{24h} and t_{48h} (Trypan
75 blue exclusion assay, calculated from **Fig. S2** in reference,¹⁰), and simulated (black; this work) B16F10 cell
76 number during incubation under control conditions (i.e., non-treated cells). (d) Cancer-cell mechanisms
77 incorporated in the *in-silico* cancer model.

78 This contribution proposes an original *in-silico* approach to quantify melanoma cancer cell
79 response to helium APPJ or/and doxorubicin drug (DOX). The *in-silico* framework is informed by relevant
80 data from *in-vitro* experiments on C57BL/6 murine B16F10 melanoma cancer cells, following results
81 published by Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*¹⁰ Thus, APPJ and DOX features, cell treatment protocols and
82 viability/cytotoxicity assessments are described there. The selected *in-vitro* experiments from,¹⁰ on which
83 the construction of the *in-silico* model was based are graphically represented in **Fig. 1**. In brief, **Fig. 1(a)**
84 depicts DOX or/and APPJ application to RPMI-1640 medium (hereafter denoted RPMI) being in contact

85 with the cancer cells. Following their exposure to DOX or/and APPJ, cancer cells are incubated for 48 h
86 (t_{48h}) and their viability is determined afterwards [Fig. 1(b)]. Based on this information, three cell-treatment
87 scenarios, experimentally investigated in¹⁰ (see Fig. 2 there), are also considered in the *in-silico* model: (i)
88 B16F10 cells in RPMI are exposed only to DOX (concentration: $c_{DOX}=0.05-0.5 \mu\text{M}$), (ii) RPMI without
89 cancer cells is subjected to APPJ only (duration: $d_{plasma}=15-120 \text{ s}$) and the resulting plasma-conditioned
90 RPMI (PC-RPMI) is put in contact with B16F10 cells (indirect plasma treatment), and (iii) B16F10 cells
91 in RPMI are exposed to DOX ($c_{DOX}=0.05$ and $0.1 \mu\text{M}$) and then subjected to APPJ for 15 s (direct plasma
92 treatment). In each ‘treatment case’ scenario, the evolution of B16F10 cell number during incubation is
93 simulated with *in-silico* results fitted to the experimental data [like for the control in Fig. 1(c)].

94 The proposed *in-silico* approach employs the agent-based modeling method²² (ABM) to simulate
95 the *in-vitro* experiments of B16F10 cancer cells performed by Pefani-Antimisiari *et al*¹⁰ –a relevant *in-*
96 *silico* in concept approach to simulate glioblastoma cells is presented in de Montigny *et al*.²³ In brief, ABM
97 is a complex-system method that models autonomous and interactive agents, denoted as particles positioned
98 in space.²⁴ As with the *in-vitro*, a two-dimensional space is assumed where agents can freely move in a
99 square plane (4.84 mm^2) providing restrictions for agent—agent overlap and collapse. Periodic boundary
100 conditions are applied at the sides of the 2D square, while temporal resolution in our simulations assumes
101 a 1-hour time increment [like in Fig. 1(c); black]. The behavior of each agent is determined after accounting
102 in simple rules and interactions with other agents, as well as with respect to external stimuli, here PC-RPMI,
103 DOX, and DOX combined with APPJ. Thus, agents represent here individual B16F10 cancer cells. They
104 are modelled to grow, migrate, divide, and die [apoptosis; see Fig. 1(d)], with the latter two mechanisms
105 of cell behavior being modulated by the effect of the cytotoxic drug, DOX, while PC-RPMI and APPJ
106 modulate apoptosis only. Contrary to this, cell growth and migration are unaffected by those external
107 stimuli. The likelihood (probability) for cell migration and cell growth is fixed to 99% and 50%
108 respectively, whereas the probability for cell apoptosis and division (either programmable or induced by
109 DOX and/or PC-RPMI/APPJ) is parametrically investigated in the results that follow. Cell migration
110 combines a random walk movement (average rate: $1 \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$) and O_2 -gradient chemotaxis (maximum rate:
111 $5 \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$). The cells’ mechanical interactions (when in proximity) are modelled through Newton repellant
112 forces, while cell adhesion is neglected to reflect the conditions of matrix cells’ suspension in the RPMI.
113 The ABM describes drug and plasma-generated RONS as a “substance” whose concentration is assumed
114 homogeneous everywhere in the simulated domain of the well; hence, their transport inside the well is
115 almost instantaneous (diffusion is neglected) while no dissipation is accounted in the extracellular space.
116 Regarding the *in-silico* initial conditions, $N_0=700$ cells are considered to match the experimentally-
117 measured density of $\sim 25 \times 10^3$ cells per well (considering an average $25 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$ cell diameter),¹⁰ while c_{DOX}

118 and d_{Plasma} are set accordingly to reflect each ‘treatment case’ scenario. ABM is implemented in the C++
119 project *invitro_neuro*,²⁵ which employs the open-source software platform *BioDynaMo*.²⁶

120 **FIG. 2.** Simulated B16F10 cell number after (a) 4 h (t_{4h}) and (b) 48 h (t_{48h}) of incubation. (c) Cell apoptosis
121 (black) and mitosis (red) probability values evaluated *in-silico* after 5 statistically-independent ABM
122 simulations. Black and red dashed lines represent mean apoptosis and mitosis probability values from those
123 5 simulations, respectively. This image refers to the control experiment (non-treated cancer cells).

124 **Figs. 2(a)** and **2(b)** depict indicative simulated cell population number (N_{cell}) developments at t_{4h}
125 and t_{48h} under control conditions [a full **Animation** (t_0 — t_{48h}) is available in the **supplementary material**;
126 cell colors represent different cell ages, as explained there]. N_{cell} is obtained from **Fig. 1(c)** by appropriately
127 fitting *in-silico* (black; this work) to *in-vitro* data (red; calculated based on **Fig. S2** from reference¹⁰). Indeed,

128 at t_{4h} in **Figs. 1(c)** and **2(a)**, the simulated N_{cell} is very close to N_0 , as for the *in-vitro* experiment. Then, at
129 t_{24h} the model predicts a ~7-fold increase in N_{cell} [$\sim 36\%$ lower than the corresponding *in-vitro* value; see
130 **Fig 1(c)**], while at t_{48h} , it predicts a ~30-fold increase in N_{cell} with respect to N_0 [**Figs. 1(c)** and **2(b)**], being
131 only ~12% higher than for the experiment. Therefore, the *in-silico* model is very complementary to the *in-*
132 *vitro* experiments. In addition, the model provides real-time quantification [1-hour time increment; black
133 data in **Fig. 1(c)**] and visualization [**Figs. 2(a)** and **(b)**] of N_{cell} during incubation. This is practically not
134 feasible with *in-vitro* experiments [red; **Fig. 1(c)**] due to the need of using time-consuming cell-viability
135 assays (e.g., MTT and Trypan blue) and expensive B16F10 melanoma cell vials. Furthermore, to
136 appropriately simulate N_{cell} development between t_0 and t_{48h} , the model easily encompasses and analyzes
137 different probability values for cancer cell apoptosis ($\%P_{Apoptosis}$) and mitosis ($\%P_{Mitosis}$) (or other cell
138 mechanisms if needed). Then, for each ‘treatment case’ scenario, it returns optimal $\%P_{Apoptosis}$ and $\%P_{Mitosis}$
139 to achieve the best agreement between *in-vitro* and *in-silico* data [like in **Fig. 1(c)** for the control]. This
140 further reduces the need of sophisticated flow cytometry experiments for exposing different cancer cell
141 mechanisms (e.g., Annexin V and Propidium Iodide staining for detecting apoptotic and necrotic cells
142 respectively).¹⁰ Here, the optimal simulated $\%P_{Apoptosis}$ and $\%P_{Mitosis}$ for the control are presented in **Fig.**
143 **2(c)**. $\%P_{Apoptosis}$ varies between $15.31 \pm 0.14\%$ and $18.92 \pm 0.24\%$ giving an average $\%P_{Apoptosis}$ of
144 $17.54 \pm 1.72\%$. However, $\%P_{Mitosis}$ obtains clearly larger values between $22.74 \pm 0.08\%$ and $24.98 \pm 0.04\%$
145 resulting in an average $\%P_{Mitosis}$ of $23.72 \pm 1.1\%$, i.e., ~6% higher than for the apoptosis. Using those average
146 probabilities, the calculated apoptosis-to-mitosis ratio (R_{A-M}) is $\sim 0.73 \pm 0.04$ under control conditions. Thus,
147 when cancer cells remain untreated, they are more prone to undergo mitotic than apoptotic mechanisms,
148 which leads to their substantial proliferation at t_{48h} [**Fig. 2(b)**]. In the following, this R_{A-M} value will be
149 referred to as a critical threshold to identify and assess the impact on B16F10 cell number/viability of PC-
150 RPMI, DOX and DOX combined with APPJ. Specifically, larger R_{A-M} than the previous threshold would
151 mean enhanced $\%P_{Apoptosis}$ and/or reduced $\%P_{Mitosis}$ for cancer cells and, thus, smaller viability and N_{cell} . In
152 the following figures, mean values and standard deviation bars correspond to 5 statistically-independent
153 experiments.

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157 **FIG. 3.** Simulated B16F10 cell number at t_{48h} following subjection to PC-RPMI at (a) $d_{plasma}=15$ s and (b)
 158 $d_{plasma}=120$ s. (c) Cancer-cell apoptosis-to-mitosis ratio evaluated *in-silico* as a function of d_{plasma} .

159 **Fig. 3** illustrates the simulation results about the effect on B16F10 cell dynamics and mechanisms
 160 of PC-RPMI under different d_{plasma} . All data refer to t_{48h} , i.e., end of incubation. Comparison of **Fig. 3(a)**
 161 against **Fig. 2(b)** (control) shows that, for $d_{plasma}=15$ s, PC-RPMI has a negligible role in the decrease of
 162 cell viability/number. However, an 8-fold increase of d_{plasma} [**Fig. 3(b)**] drives into an approximately 20
 163 times smaller N_{cell} with respect to the control experiment (also see **Figs. S1(a)** and **S1(b)** in the
 164 **supplementary material**). Therefore, B16F10 cell viability is significantly reduced due to their interaction
 165 with larger amounts of long-lived RONS in PC-RPMI (H_2O_2 , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , etc.). Those species have

166 demonstrated synergism in inducing strong cytotoxic effects on cancers depending on their
167 concentration.^{2,6-9} Furthermore, **Fig. 3(c)** illustrates the dependence of R_{A-M} on d_{Plasma} . At $d_{Plasma}=15$ s, R_{A-M}
168 is almost the same with the control threshold (dashed red) resulting in similar cell dynamics [**Fig. 3(a)** and
169 **Fig. 2(b)**, respectively]. As so, $d_{Plasma}=15$ s cannot lead to significant modification of the medium's
170 chemistry, and it is not suitable for enhanced B16F10 cell apoptosis and viability decrease. The PC-RPMI
171 impact starts to become noticeable after $d_{Plasma}=30$ s. Indeed, the corresponding R_{A-M} is 0.93 ± 0.03 and it
172 goes up to 1.26 ± 0.03 at $d_{Plasma}=120$ s, which is approximately 27 and 73% larger respectively, as compared
173 to the control threshold. Therefore, our simulations reveal that %P_{Apoptosis} (see **Fig. S1(c)**) is increasingly
174 promoted when increasing d_{Plasma} . Note that in **Fig. 3**, %P_{Mitosis} was kept the same as that of the control
175 ($23.72\%\pm 1.1\%$; **Fig. S1(c)**). In fact, we are not aware of any published study reporting on enhanced or
176 suppressed effects of PC-RPMI on B16F10 murine melanoma cell mitosis with increasing d_{Plasma} .

177 The *in-silico* results demonstrating the DOX effect on B16F10 cell dynamics and mechanisms are
178 illustrated in **Fig. 4**. The simulated N_{cell} corresponding to the smallest c_{DOX} [0.05 μM ; **Fig. 4(a)**] is ~ 1.4
179 times smaller than that of the control [**Fig. 2(b)**; also see **Fig. S2(a)** in the **supplementary material**]. When
180 compared to the smallest d_{Plasma} in **Fig. 3(a)**, this c_{DOX} is more effective in reducing cell number/viability.
181 In fact, at $d_{Plasma}=15$ s, it is expected that the amount of long-lived RONS (H_2O_2 , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , etc.) generated
182 by the APPJ in the RPMI is not sufficient to induce significant apoptosis in cancer cells.^{8,9,12} Furthermore,
183 at the largest c_{DOX} of 0.5 μM in **Fig. 4(b)**, a drastic drop in N_{cell} is revealed [about 22-fold reduction with
184 respect to control; **Fig. S2(b)**]. These results can be further analyzed by studying the dependence of R_{A-M}
185 on c_{DOX} [**Fig. 4(c)**]. First, the R_{A-M} corresponding to $c_{DOX}=0.05$ μM is by $\sim 7\%$ larger than for the control
186 threshold (dashed red). From **Fig. S2(c)**, this increase is due to slightly larger %P_{Apoptosis} and smaller %P_{Mitosis}
187 at this drug concentration. Furthermore, when c_{DOX} is increased (0.1 – 0.2 μM), R_{A-M} becomes $\sim 13.5\%$ larger
188 than for the control threshold. Again, this augmentation is justified by persistently larger and smaller
189 %P_{Apoptosis} and %P_{Mitosis}, respectively, with increasing c_{DOX} [**Fig. S2(c)**]. Finally, at $c_{DOX}=0.5$ μM , the model
190 demonstrates a dramatic increase in R_{A-M} , which is $\sim 59\%$ larger than for the control threshold. From **Fig.**
191 **S2(c)**, $c_{DOX}=0.5$ μM exhibits the smallest %P_{Mitosis} and largest %P_{Apoptosis} among all c_{DOX} studied, while it is
192 the only drug concentration for which %P_{Apoptosis} is clearly larger than %P_{Mitosis}, leading to enhanced cell
193 cytotoxicity and viability decrease. It should be noted that an R_{A-M} value of 1.16 ± 0.05 in **Fig. 4(c)** ($c_{DOX}=0.5$
194 μM) could also be achieved when using PC-RPMI at $d_{Plasma}=90$ – 100 s, since for $d_{Plasma}=60$ and 120 s, the
195 corresponding R_{A-M} are 1.01 ± 0.02 and 1.26 ± 0.03 [**Fig. 3(c)**], suggesting enhanced production of long-lived
196 RONS in PC-RPMI.

197 **FIG. 4.** Simulated B16F10 cell number at t_{48h} following exposure to DOX in the RPMI at (a) $c_{DOX}=0.05$
 198 μM and (b) $c_{DOX}=0.5 \mu\text{M}$. (c) Cancer-cell apoptosis-to-mitosis ratio evaluated *in-silico* as a function of
 199 c_{DOX} in the RPMI.

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204 **FIG. 5.** Simulated B16F10 cell number at t_{48} (a) in the presence of $0.1 \mu\text{M}$ DOX in RPMI, and (b) $0.1 \mu\text{M}$
 205 DOX in RPMI treated for 15 s with APPJ. (c) Cancer-cell apoptosis-to-mitosis ratio evaluated *in-silico* for
 206 two scenarios of combined treatments using DOX and APPJ.

207 **Fig. 5** presents *in-silico* results which demonstrate the effect on B16F10 cell dynamics of combined
 208 DOX and direct APPJ treatment. To perform the investigation, the smallest two c_{DOX} from **Fig. 4(c)** (0.05
 209 and $0.1 \mu\text{M}$) and d_{plasma} from **Fig. 3(c)** (15 s) were used. This was done to obtain measurable cell numbers,
 210 since combining higher c_{DOX} and d_{plasma} would result in a critical decrease of cell viability.¹⁰ Therefore, it
 211 would be more difficult to discriminate the impact on cancer cells of the combined action of DOX and
 212 APPJ. **Fig. 5(a)** illustrates simulated cell dynamics corresponding to $c_{DOX}=0.1 \mu\text{M}$. The simulated N_{cell} in
 213 this scenario is smaller than that in **Fig. 4(a)** ($c_{DOX}=0.05 \mu\text{M}$), as imposed by the higher corresponding R_A -

214 m in **Fig. 4(c)**. Specifically, the simulated N_{cell} at $C_{\text{DOX}}=0.1 \mu\text{M}$ is ~ 2 times smaller than that for the control
215 [**Fig. 2(b)**]. However, by additionally subjecting cancer cells to $d_{\text{plasma}}=15 \text{ s}$ (in the presence of DOX), see
216 **Fig. 5(b)**, N_{cell} drops by about 4.5 times with respect to the control (see **Fig. S3(a)** in the **supplementary**
217 **material**). Thus, our simulations demonstrate a significant enhancement in cell cytotoxicity of 2.25 and ~ 4
218 times, compared to that induced only by DOX or PC-RPMI, respectively. In fact, when DOX-treated cancer
219 cells are further subjected to direct APPJ treatment, it is possible that they interact with plasma-generated
220 short-lived RONS (O, OH, NO, $^1\text{O}_2$, etc.), UV radiation and/or pulsed electric fields, which may also induce
221 cytotoxic effects.^{1,2,9,11} Finally, the dependence of R_{A-M} on the combined action of DOX and APPJ is
222 depicted in **Fig. 5(c)**. For $c_{\text{DOX}}=0.05 \mu\text{M}$ and $d_{\text{plasma}}=15 \text{ s}$, R_{A-M} is 0.87 ± 0.03 , while it goes up to 0.91 ± 0.05
223 for $c_{\text{DOX}}=0.1 \mu\text{M}$ and $d_{\text{plasma}}=15 \text{ s}$. This corresponds to an increase of $\sim 19\%$ and 24.5% with respect to the
224 control threshold (dashed red) respectively. Therefore, combining DOX with direct APPJ treatments results
225 to a larger B16F10 cell cytotoxicity. As shown in **Fig. S3(b)**, our model captures the effect of combined
226 DOX with direct plasma treatment in enhancing $\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$ and suppressing $\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$ of B16F10 melanoma
227 cells. This finding agrees with recent *in-vitro* experiments performed by Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*,¹⁰ where
228 DOX and direct APPJ treatment demonstrated a synergistic action on melanoma cell viability decline.

229 To summarize, in this work we developed a novel *in-silico* agent-based model (ABM) to simulate
230 B16F10 murine melanoma cancer cell response to helium APPJ or/and DOX. The *in-silico* model was
231 informed by relevant published data from *in-vitro* experiments on cancer cell viability (reference¹⁰) and
232 provided information on (i) N_{cell} development during incubation (48 h), and (ii) $\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$ and $\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$
233 following cancer cell subjection to plasma-conditioned RPMI (PC-RPMI), DOX, and DOX combined with
234 APPJ. The *in-silico* model revealed a significant impact on N_{cell} , $\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$ or/and $\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$ of each
235 ‘treatment case’ scenario depending on d_{plasma} and c_{DOX} , in agreement with the corresponding *in-vitro*
236 experiments. Therefore, the present ABM could be particularly useful in plasma (cancer) medicine field
237 since it can predict cancer cell behavior upon exposure to APPJ or/and DOX by quantifying cancer cell
238 apoptosis and mitosis mechanisms – other cell phenotypes, e.g., glioblastoma,²³ and cell mechanisms (e.g.,
239 growth, migration, differentiation, etc.),²⁵ can be specified in the *in-silico* model depending on the biology
240 involved, treatment type and application.

241 The reader can refer to the **supplementary material** for a dynamic visualization of *in-silico* N_{cell}
242 development during incubation under control conditions (**Animation**), and graphical comparison of the *in-*
243 *silico* (our work) and *in-vitro* (calculated from reference¹⁰) results regarding N_{cell} , $\%P_{\text{Apoptosis}}$ and $\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$
244 values in response to PC-RPMI (**Fig. S1**), DOX (**Fig. S2**) and DOX combined with APPJ (**Fig. S3**).

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265 **Data Availability Statement**

266 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
267 reasonable request.

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311
312 **Animation.** Simulated B16F10 cell population development during 48 h of incubation (t_{48h}) under control
313 conditions [also see [Figs. 1\(c\)](#) and [2](#) in the manuscript]. The different cell colors shown in the animation
314 represent different cell ages (colder colors refer to younger cells while warmer colors refer to older cells).
315 B16F10 cell age is measured from the beginning of the simulation (i.e., start of incubation; t_0) and advances
316 until the end of the incubation (t_{48h}). Cancer cells grow at a constant rate ($\%P_{\text{Growth}}$ is set fixed to 50% in all
317 ABM simulation cases) with their average diameter ranging between 20 to 30
318 μm . Cells also divide ($\%P_{\text{Mitosis}}$ is not dependent to cell age), and when they do, the age of the newly-
319 created cells is initialized zero.

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321

322 **FIG. S1.** Experimental (red; calculated based on **Fig. 2(b)** from Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*, see reference¹⁰ in
 323 the manuscript) and simulated (black; this work) B16F10 cancer cell population number at the end (t_{48h})
 324 and during incubation (0–48 h), respectively, following exposure to RPMI-1640 treated for (a) 15 s and (b)
 325 120 s with APPJ. The blue dashed line and rectangle refer to mean cell population number and standard
 326 deviation bar, respectively, in the control case. (c) Cancer-cell apoptosis probability values shown as a
 327 function of duration of plasma treatment of RPMI-1640. Mean values and standard deviation bars refer to
 328 5 statistically independent simulations. Using those probabilities, a good agreement between *in-silico* (our
 329 work) and *in-vitro* (Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*¹⁰) is achieved at t_{48h} . Here, APPJ does not impact cancer cell
 330 mitosis [mean mitosis probability (red) is kept the same as that of control in **Fig. 2** of the manuscript].

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332

333 **FIG. S2.** Experimental (red; calculated based on **Fig. 2(a)** from Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*, see reference¹⁰ in
 334 the manuscript) and simulated (black) B16F10 cancer cell population number at the end (t_{48h}) and during
 335 incubation (0–48 h), respectively, following exposure to RPMI-1640 in the presence of (a) 0.05 μM DOX
 336 and (b) 0.5 μM DOX. The blue dashed line and rectangle refer to mean cell population number and standard
 337 deviation bar, respectively, in the case of control. (c) Cancer-cell apoptosis and mitosis probability values
 338 plotted as a function of DOX concentration in RPMI-1640. Mean values and standard deviation bars refer
 339 to 5 statistically independent simulations. Using those probabilities, a good agreement between *in-silico*
 340 (our work) and *in-vitro* (Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*¹⁰) is achieved at t_{48h} . Here, DOX impacts both cancer cell
 341 apoptosis (black) and mitosis (red).

342

343

344 **FIG. S3.** (a) Experimental (red; calculated based on **Figs. 2(c)** and **2(d)** from Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*, see
 345 reference¹⁰ in the manuscript) and simulated (black) B16F10 cancer cell population number at the end (t_{48h})
 346 and during incubation (0–48 h), respectively, in the presence of 0.1 μM DOX in RPMI-1640 plasma-treated
 347 for 15 s. The blue dashed line and rectangle refer to mean cell population number and standard deviation
 348 bar, respectively, in the case of control. (b) Cancer-cell apoptosis and mitosis probability values predicted
 349 for two scenarios of combined treatments using DOX (0.05 or 0.1 μM) and plasma (15 s). Mean values and
 350 standard deviation bars refer to 5 statistically independent simulations. Using the simulated apoptosis and
 351 mitosis probability values corresponding to combined treatment of 0.1 μM DOX and 15 s plasma, a good
 352 agreement between *in-silico* (our work) and *in-vitro* (Pefani-Antimisiari *et al.*¹⁰) is achieved at t_{48h} .